

whereas riboflavin has higher triplet energy and all the dyes having higher triplet energies generate more $^1\Sigma_g$ oxygen and less $^1\Delta_g$ oxygen and vice versa.

Further, the drastic reduction in the yield of the product in the presence of scavengers confirms that the singlet oxygen is the active oxidising species in the photo-oxygenation of amithiazone.

Experimental

Amithiazone (0.5 g) dissolved in methanol (40 ml) containing methylene blue ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) was exposed to a tungsten lamp kept at a distance of 20 cm from the lower surface of the reaction flask. Oxygen gas was continuously bubbled through the solution. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc using the solvent system n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5, v/v). The

resulting, solid, m.p. 118° (identified as sulphur) was filtered out. The filtrate was decolourised with active charcoal and evaporated to yield a residue which was crystallised from alcohol.

References

1. J. P. JOWIN and BUN-HOI, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur (Paris)*, 1946, 76, 580.
2. J. J. WORMAN, M. SHEN and P. C. NICHOLS, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1972, 50, 3923; C. C. WAMSER and J. W. HERRING, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1976, 41, 1476; R. DUBBY, P. GANDHI, S. JAIN and M. M. BOKADIA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1985, 54, 340.
3. R. H. YOUNG, D. BREWER and R. A. KELLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95, 375.
4. D. R. KEARNS, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1969, 10, 215; K. ESKINS, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1979, 29, 609.
5. D. J. CARLSSON, T. SPRUNCHUK and D. M. WILES, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1974, 52, 3728.
6. P. B. PUNJABI, S. C. AMETA, T. C. SHARMA and M. M. BOKADIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 130.

A Simple Conversion of Carboxylic Acids into Carboxamides

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The transformation of carboxylic acids to carboxamides is a known procedure¹. Newer synthetic methods are still being reported for this conversion^{2,3}. However, most of the methods have limitation mainly due to the use of too drastic reaction condition or expensive reagents. In the present communication we describe a facile method for converting carboxylic acids into carboxamides by adding judiciously the amine to ethyl dichlorophosphate generated *in situ* and then reacting with stoichiometric amounts of the acid. The carboxamide formation proceeds via a substituted phosphoramidic acid ethyl ester⁴ and is complete within a short period of time at room temperature. The carboxamides thus formed are chromatographically and spectroscopically pure. The method is good both for aliphatic and aromatic carboxylic acids carboxamides of primary and secondary amines.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a Büchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer PE 580 B spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra on a Varian T-60 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a AEI-MS-30 spectrometer.

General procedure: To a stirred solution of $POCl_3$ (10 mmol, 1.5 g) was added gradually dry ethanol (10 mmol, 0.6 ml) followed by aniline

(20 mmol, 1.86 g) and the mixture was stirred for 15 min. Benzoic acid (20 mmol, 2.44 g) in triethylamine (20 mmol, 3 ml) and dry dichloromethane (25 ml) was slowly added into the reaction mixture and it was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, aqueous 10% $NaHCO_3$ and water. After drying over sodium sulphate, it was evaporated to dryness to give benzanilide (3.6 g, 92%), m.p. 164°, M^+ 197; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 660 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ ($CDCl_3$) 6.5—7.6 (10H, m, ArH) and 5.6 (1H, b, NH).

Salicylamide, *N*-benzylbenzamide, *N*-benzylsalicylamide, *N*-*m*-tolylbenzamide, anthranilide, *N*-isopropylanthranilamide, acetanilide, *N*-morpholinosalicylamide and *N*-*p*-anisylbenzamide were prepared in similar way. The observed m.ps. were as per literature³. The physical and spectroscopic data of some carboxamides are given below: salicylanilide (90%), m. p. 136°; M^+ 213; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 645 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ ($CDCl_3$ -DMSO- d_6) 5.2 (1H, b, amide), 6.4—8.0 (9H, m, ArH) and 11.8 (1H, s, phenolic); anthranilide (90%), m.p. 118°; M^+ 212; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 650 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ ($CDCl_3$ -DMSO- d_6) 5.0 (1H, b, amide), 6.2 (2H, b, NH) and 6.5—7.7 (9H, m, ArH); *N*-isopropyl anthranilide (87%), m.p. 147°; M^+ 178; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 665 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ ($CDCl_3$ -DMSO- d_6) 1.2 (6H, d,